

Demonstration that attribution of a probability density function to a constant leads to a logical contradiction

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Abstract

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Summary

This article examines the claim that a meaningful probability distribution can be attributed to an unknown constant existing on a continuous scale. Such a distribution is thought to describe the belief of the person making the probability statement, and this belief is regarded as being amenable to logical analysis on receipt of new information. We examine the implications of this joint claim – that a probability density function can be attributed to a constant and can be updated logically — and we demonstrate that they lead to a logical contradiction: when disjoint sets of information are received, the combined density function that ensues depends on an arbitrary parametrization. This analysis brings to the attention of the general reader a result that has come to light in the measurement literature. The result challenges one basis of Bayesian statistical practice, so an attempt is made to understand how this phenomenon can arise. The result is only demonstrated for constants on a continuous scale: constants that are attributed probability mass functions are not affected.

Keywords: Bayesian statistics; degree of belief; subjective probability; fiducial probability; reasoning

1 Introduction

Probability is an abstract mathematical concept that obeys axioms. For many statisticians, the role of probability is restricted to the description of relative frequency in a hypothetically repeatable experiment. However, for others, probability can also be used to describe personal doubt about an unknown constant, so that the constant is treated as a random variable with a known distribution. In the Bayesian context, the claim is that a person's 'degree of belief' about a constant can be treated as a subjective probability and that subsequent reasoning can proceed as if that constant were a random variable. Here, we examine the theoretical basis for the updating of subjective probability and we demonstrate that, when it is applied to a constant on a continuous scale, it leads to logical contradiction. We suggest that the identification of degree of belief with probability is an unjustified premise and that *reasoning with belief is not the same as reasoning with probability*. Some of the material here appears novel, and some of the material presents results described in the literature of metrology (measurement science) (Willink, 2021, 2022, 2024, 2025)(Grientschnig and Lira, 2014), where there is ongoing debate about the nature of a globally recommended method for the evaluation of 'uncertainty in measurement', i.e., the analysis of measurement error.

The subject of this paper is the idea that a probability distribution can be attributed to an unknown constant to adequately reflect the speaker's belief about it. The basic claims or principles underlying this use of probability theory are as follows:

1. A person's uncertainty about (the true value of) a constant quantity θ can be fully and logically represented by a probability distribution for θ .
2. Probability assignments relating to θ made by the same person are to be self-consistent.
3. A probability distribution for θ is to be updated in a sensible manner when relevant new information is received.
4. When this information comes from an experiment with a sampling model, Bayes' theorem is the means by which this updating is carried out.

The paper is concerned with the validity of statement 1, which is a statement that this author regards as

an unproven premise. The truth of statement 1 is not something self-evident and so, like other claims, statement 1 requires proof or justification before general acceptance. If it is true and if the probability distribution for θ has any real meaning or importance then statements 2 and 3 are corollaries. But here we show that if we accept statements 2 and 3 then, in general, we obtain a logical contradiction, which implies that statement 1 is false or devoid of meaning.

The result of this paper has major implications for the practice of Bayesian statistics. However, this is not a paper about the validity or nature of Bayes' theorem. So the relevance of statement 4 to this paper is minimal. However, statement 4 serves two functions here: (a) it supports statement 3 in as much as the requirement for sensibleness, i.e., rationality, is reflected in the emphasis it gives to the application of Bayes' theorem and (b) it hints at the idea that new information about θ can be received in a different form. Just as Bayes' theorem would be the appropriate tool when there is indirect information about θ found in an experiment where θ is a model parameter, a suitable tool must exist (potentially at least) for when new information about θ arrives in another form. Therefore, in this paper, we will consider new information that is similar in nature to the direct information from which a person consciously or unconsciously constructs their initial distribution for θ . We show that statements 1–3 are internally inconsistent in that context, and we neither question statement 4 nor apply Bayes's theorem. Thus, we consider the receipt of information that — by itself — would lead the person to form a different probability distribution for θ , one that is to be combined in a rational manner with the original distribution in the updating process. We will obtain contradictory results that demonstrate statement 1 to be unacceptable as a universal claim.

Section 2 introduces the principle on which our analysis rests, presents a corresponding set of statements that follow from statements 1–3, and then gives a simple demonstration of how a contradiction ensues. Section 3 then examines that principle, which is the idea that we can conceive of separate sets of information that form belief in an additive and commutative manner. Section 4 strengthens our conclusion using an argument that exists in the measurement literature. Section 5 seeks to explain how the contradiction can exist in an environment where Bayesian theory is highly regarded, and Section 6 concludes.

Before proceeding, let us discuss matters of terminology. In practice, the word 'information' is often used loosely and ambiguously. Does it refer to something that is necessarily true, as in the field of 'information

theory’ that emerged from Shannon’s communication theory? Or is there such a thing as false information? This distinction is relevant here because the view that there can be an objective form of Bayesian statistics is a view based on the idea that ‘information’ is correct and can be quantified. But the subjectivist forms his or her strength of belief not just from facts but also from subjective impressions. So, instead of regularly using the word ‘information’, we shall often use the word ‘influence’ to act as a countable noun that describes an element in the total experience of a person who forms their probability distribution for θ , be it a piece of correct information or a subjective impression.

We will also describe acceptable reasoning as being ‘sensible’ rather than ‘rational’. This is because the term ‘rational belief’ is associated with the ‘necessary’ or ‘logical’ view of probability, and we do not want to distract the reader from the fact that the conclusions apply to the idea of subjective probability as well as to the idea of necessary probability. However, the word ‘sensible’ here can be interpreted as meaning ‘rational’.

2 Demonstration of a contradiction

2.1 Preliminaries

Let there be an unknown constant θ that exists on a continuous scale. If any quantitative analysis about θ is to carry weight then the steps involved in that analysis must follow acceptable reasoning. So, any probability distribution that a person attributes to θ must be formed as a sensible response to all the relevant influences on that person’s thinking, be they elemental pieces of information or elemental impressions, be they consciously identified or not. With regard to belief about θ , the person’s state of mind is an aggregate of all these influences.

More specifically, we assert that if we can conceive of two disjoint sets of influences that, separately, would lead a person to attribute probability density functions (PDFs) $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ to θ , then when both these sets of influences are experienced, in accordance with statements 1–4,

- i. there is a unique combined PDF $f(x)$ that corresponds to the rational combination of $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$,

- ii. no other information is needed to obtain $f(x)$.

In support of these two assertions, we observe that — according to statement 1 — the states of uncertainty about θ caused in the mind of the person by the individual sets of influences are fully described by the two distributions. Aggregating the sets of influences introduces nothing and loses nothing, so the combined distribution must be formed from the two individual distributions and only from these distributions.

The second assertion is important for another reason. It implies that each contributing distribution carries equal weight. Following statement 1, each distribution is a complete and correct description of the person's uncertainty if they had only experienced the influences in the corresponding set of influences. Neither distribution is more correct or reliable than the other. But that does not mean that each is equally influential; rather, the relative strengths of the sets of influences represented by a distribution will be associated with the widths of those distributions, as summarized in their standard deviations.

(There is perhaps a misconception about this among many applied scientists who seek to embrace Bayesian thinking. Some might think that θ possesses a unique distribution to be found by combining the different PDFs according to the reliability of the information on which they were based, so that the reliabilities and authorities of the functions $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ become important. But θ is a constant whose only attributes are an unknown magnitude and a state of constancy. The type of probability distribution in question is not an attribute of θ : it is an attribute of the person who is making the statements of probability, and these statements are to be based on sensible conscious or subconscious appreciation of all the relevant influences experienced. So the second assertion emphasizes that $f(x)$ is to be found from $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ alone, and it implies that the sets of influences that would generate $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ in the mind of the speaker have been fully accepted. So there are no unequal weights than can or should be associated with the PDFs $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$: the strengths of these PDFs are already reflected in the corresponding standard deviations.)

Thus, we further assert that if statements 1–4 apply with a continuous-valued quantity θ then the following statements also apply.

5. A PDF attributed to a quantity θ existing on a continuous scale is to be a sensible response to a set of impressions and information (which here we jointly call 'influences') about θ .
6. Two sets of influences about θ can be disjoint, and these sets of influences would individually generate

two distinct PDFs in the mind of the speaker.

7. There must (potentially at least) be a unique correct way to combine these PDFs to reflect experiencing both sets of influences.
8. The resulting PDF depends only on the two contributions, not on any auxiliary information about these contributions.

In this way, we require the rationality that is seen in the process of updating by Bayes' theorem to also exist in a process of reasoning about separate sets of influences on the speaker.

Our analysis is then based on the idea that we can conceive of two disjoint sets of potential influences on the belief of a person, as is expressed in statement 6. The validity of this idea seemed to be questioned by one noted Bayesian writer in discussion with this author. It is a non-trivial idea that must be discussed further before the results of this paper can be fully accepted, but we leave further justification of this idea until Section 3.

2.2 Argument

Consider an idealized probabilistic assessment of unknown constants θ and $\lambda \equiv \theta^2$. For example, θ could be the unknown length of the side of a square object and λ could be the area. Suppose that one set of influences would cause a particular person to attribute θ a continuous uniform distribution on the unit interval $(0, 1]$ and suppose that an unrelated set of influences would cause them to attribute θ the uniform distribution on the interval $(0, 2]$. The first set of influences is stronger in the sense that it precludes the possibility that $\theta > 1$, but neither distribution would give any cause to consider any value in the interval $(0, 1]$ to be more likely than any other. So if the person had received *both* sets of influences then they would attribute θ the uniform distribution on the interval $(0, 1]$. Consequently — by the familiar idea of the transformation of random variables — the person would attribute λ the PDF $f_\lambda(y) = \frac{1}{2}y^{-1/2}$ for $0 \leq y \leq 1$, as depicted in Figure 1(a).

Figure 1: The density functions (a) $f(y) = \frac{1}{2}y^{-1/2}$ for $0 \leq y \leq 1$ and (b) $f(y) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{4}}y^{-1/2}$ for $0 \leq y \leq 4$, which correspond to the (power-function) distributions that we denote by $P[0,1]$ and $P[0,4]$.

Let $U[0, a]$ indicate the continuous uniform distribution on the interval $(0, a]$, and let $P[0, b]$ indicate the (power-function) distribution of a variable with the PDF

$$f(y) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{b}}y^{-1/2} \quad 0 \leq y \leq b.$$

Then this process of reasoning is symbolized in Figure 2, where (beginning at the top-left) the person combines (C) the two uniform densities for θ and moves to the top-right before transforming (T) to the final PDF for λ at the bottom-right. The result from this reasoning is that λ is attributed the distribution $P[0, 1]$.

Figure 2: Interchangeable methods of reasoning that do not lead to the same conclusion: Combining (C) and transforming (T) versus transforming and combining

The person’s final pattern of belief about λ cannot depend on whether they combine the individual sets of influences about θ and then transform to λ or transform the individual PDFs and then combine. So let us consider the alternative path from top-left to bottom-right in Figure 2. Transforming the individual distributions $U[0, 1]$ and $U[0, 2]$ for θ gives the individual distributions of $P[0, 1]$ and $P[0, 4]$ for λ — whose PDFs are shown in Figure 1(a) and Figure 1(b) — and brings us to the bottom-left corner in Figure 2, where these two PDFs are to be combined. We see that if the result is to be invariant then combining the distributions $P[0, 1]$ and $P[0, 4]$ obtained from the separate sets of influences must result in $P[0, 1]$. In other words, if the person has experienced a set of influences that causes them to attribute the distribution $P[0, 1]$ to λ then subsequently experiencing a separate set of influences that, by itself, would have induced the distribution $P[0, 4]$ — which is non-uniform over its entire domain and especially over the unit interval — can make no change to their initial pattern of belief! This does not make sense: it is as if the second set of influences is being disregarded, as if it contained no information or had no merit. The step of rationally combining the distributions $P[0, 1]$ and $P[0, 4]$ when they represent disjoint sets of influences about a constant cannot possibly result in $P[0, 1]$, and that is indicated at the bottom of Figure 2 by striking through the relevant symbols.

So, taking different paths in this diagram leads to two different results, and yet these results must logically be the same if the paradigm of inference is valid. The only possible explanation for this contradiction is that there is something faulty in the premise of the analysis, which is the premise that a PDF can be attributed to a

constant, as in statement 1. (The quadratic relationship between θ and λ is not required for the contradiction to exist: it just makes the illustration intuitive.)

Somehow we have observed an internal inconsistency: we have (i) accepted statement 1 and its corollaries 2–3, (ii) imagined the existence of two separate sets of influences that individually would generate in a person’s mind two different distributions for a single constant θ , and (iii) followed rational thought processes involving the combination of the distributions and the transformation of variables. Yet we have obtained a contradiction. In essence, this contradiction is the same as the contradiction to be demonstrated in a more thorough manner in Section 4. In the author’s opinion, this contradiction supports the conclusion that — as a universal statement — statement 1 is false.

This conclusion has been reached using the ideas that two sets of influences on belief can be disjoint and that the effects of such sets of influences are to be combined in an exhaustive additive manner. These ideas are clarified and demonstrated in Section 3. It is worth noting that our emphasis on the idea that the two sets of influences are disjoint is only for convenience: it enables the method of combination to be identified, which enables a contradiction to be demonstrated. We are not claiming that subjective distributions for θ are formed in this unit-by-unit manner, just that they *might be* formed in this manner. So, strictly, our conclusion is that statement 1 is incorrect *as a principle*.

3 Disjoint sets of influences

To demonstrate the contradiction, we have put forward the idea that two sets of influences contributing to a pattern of belief can be disjoint. The formation of the final distribution for θ would involve the sensible aggregation of these marginal effects. This idea does not seem mentioned in any way in Bayesian texts, which lack discussion of the psychological aspects of the formation of a prior degree of belief. We now consider whether this idea of aggregation is acceptable.

3.1 Existence

One Bayesian author who was contacted at an early stage in this work seemed to question the idea that in practice two sets of information would ever be disjoint. To that I would respond, “The result is not about practice; it is about the theoretical underpinning of practice. So the study of idealized situations is both meaningful and permitted.”

However, the fact that there can be disjoint sets of influences that individually would lead to PDFs $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ is easily demonstrated using an illustration from the field of measurement science. Let θ be the unknown mass of an object, and let $f_1(x)$ be the PDF you attribute to θ after you have carried out your complete measurement procedure (if you are inclined to see such attribution as a meaningful practice). Imagine that you are subsequently told by someone trustworthy that the object was randomly selected from the output of a manufacturing process known to produce objects with masses following a frequency distribution with density $g(x)$. This is new information that you must take into account. It is evident that if you had this new information in isolation then you would attribute a different PDF, say $f_2(x)$, to the mass θ . And it is clear — but not necessary for our argument — that you would set $f_2(x) = g(x)$. Therefore, you are in possession of two PDFs $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ for θ that are formed from entirely separate sets of influences. You now have been subject to a combined set of influences, and — following statements 7 and 8 — you must accurately encode your subsequent belief about θ in an updated, combined, PDF.

3.2 Aggregation

It is one thing to conclude that disjoint sets of influences exist, as in statement 6. But it is another matter to conclude that their effects are fully additive, as in statements 7 and 8 and in the two assertions at the beginning of Section 2.1. So let us comment further on the idea that the combined effect is, in some sense, a sum of the two individual effects. The idea is that, on the condition that the functions $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ are accurate and complete expressions of your uncertainty when you experience two disjoint sets of influences individually, the expression of your uncertainty when you are given them both, $f(x)$, must be found using the functions $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ and must be found from them alone.

I can imagine that a critic of this notion might argue “There is no fixed process or rule by which a fact or

impression becomes a degree of belief, so there is no need for the associated degrees of belief to combine according to any rule (either known or unknown). Thus, there does not need to be a rule (either known or unknown) that connects the final distribution $f(x)$ to the individual distributions $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$.” But this would seem to me to be an evasive and inconsistent argument. What is the qualitative difference between aggregating the facts or impressions of the direct type and aggregating the information contained in the prior distribution and the elements of a sample, which is certainly carried out using the rule of Bayes? If there are no rules (known or unknown) by which a prior belief is formed in the mind then there must be doubt as to whether the rule of subsequently applying Bayes’ theorem is necessary at all. There is no authority to be found in a quantitative analysis where only one step in the analysis is required to obey quantitative rules.

4 A more complete demonstration

The demonstration of the contradiction given in Section 2 seems novel, but the alternative demonstration given in this section has already appeared in the measurement literature. Again, (i) we consider the combination of probability distributions for a continuous-valued quantity, (ii) the method of combination applies when the sets of influences on the person are disjoint and (iii) the contradiction involves the transformation of variables. But the argument here is more complicated, and it might also seem more contrived. It began as an argument against the idea that ‘necessary probability’ can accurately represent objective information (Willink, 2021) — which is an unsatisfactory idea that seems to appeal to many applied scientists — but it has been extended to also apply to the concept of subjective probability (Willink, 2025). Here we broadly follow the most recent published description (Willink, 2025).

4.1 The combination of PDFs derived from separate influences

Let θ_1 and θ_2 be unknown constants that exist on a continuous scale, let S_1 and S_2 be respective disjoint sets of impressions or information, and let $f_1(x_1)$ and $f_2(x_2)$ be the respective PDFs for θ_1 and θ_2 that are induced in the speaker by these sets of influences. Let δ be a unit of discretization, let $\acute{\theta}_1$ and $\acute{\theta}_2$ be the values of θ_1 and θ_2 when they are rounded onto a discrete scale with values $\dots - 2\delta, -\delta, 0, \delta, 2\delta, \dots$, and let

$p_1(x)$ and $p_2(x)$ be the corresponding probability mass functions for $\hat{\theta}_1$ and $\hat{\theta}_2$. (So $p_j(x) = \int_{x-\delta/2}^{x+\delta/2} f_j(z)dz$.) Then, in the speaker's thinking, $\hat{\theta}_1$ and $\hat{\theta}_2$ are independent discrete random variables with probability mass functions (PMFs) $p_1(x)$ and $p_2(x)$, the independence arising because the sets of influences that they represent are disjoint. Therefore, the joint PMF attributed to $\hat{\theta}_1$ and $\hat{\theta}_2$ is

$$\Pr(\hat{\theta}_1 = x_1 \cap \hat{\theta}_2 = x_2) = p_1(x_1)p_2(x_2).$$

An example is given in Figure 3(a), where $(p_1(1), p_1(2), p_1(3), p_1(4), p_1(5)) = (0.1, 0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2)$, $(p_2(3), p_2(4), p_2(5), p_2(6)) = (0.1, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2)$ and $\delta = 1$.

Figure 3: (a) Example joint probability mass function $\Pr(\hat{\theta}_1 = x_1 \cap \hat{\theta}_2 = x_2)$ for the PMFs $(p_1(1), p_1(2), p_1(3), p_1(4), p_1(5)) = (0.1, 0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2)$ and $(p_2(3), p_2(4), p_2(5), p_2(6)) = (0.1, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2)$ when these PMFs are formed from disjoint sets of influences. (b) Corresponding joint probability mass function on the condition that $\hat{\theta}_1 = \hat{\theta}_2$. (Empty cells have mass zero.)

Now suppose that the speaker learns that θ_1 and θ_2 are equal, so he or she also learns that $\hat{\theta}_1$ and $\hat{\theta}_2$ are

equal. On the condition that $\hat{\theta}_1 = \hat{\theta}_2$, the probability that $\hat{\theta}_1$ and $\hat{\theta}_2$ are equal to any dummy figure x is

$$\Pr \left(\hat{\theta}_1 = \hat{\theta}_2 = x \mid \hat{\theta}_1 = \hat{\theta}_2 \right) = \frac{p_1(x) p_2(x)}{\sum_z p_1(z) p_2(z)}, \quad (1)$$

as depicted in Figure 3(b) for the unconditional distribution of Figure 3(a). There is now only one unknown quantity, which we rename θ , with its discretized version being $\hat{\theta}$. Therefore, the speaker must subsequently regard $\hat{\theta}$ as a discrete random variable with PMF

$$p(x) = \frac{p_1(x) p_2(x)}{\sum_z p_1(z) p_2(z)}. \quad (2)$$

It does not matter whether the information that θ_1 and θ_2 are equal, call it S_3 , is received before or after the speaker experiences the two sets of influences S_1 and S_2 , i.e., it makes no difference to the final set of influences $S_1 \cup S_2 \cup S_3$ whether S_3 is received first or last. So, for that person, (2) must also represent the correct combination of PMFs $p_1(x)$ and $p_2(x)$ that correspond to two disjoint sets of influences about the single quantity, $\hat{\theta}$.

Equation (2) can be written as

$$\frac{p(x)}{\delta} = \frac{p_1(x)/\delta \times p_2(x)/\delta}{\sum_z p_1(z)/\delta \times p_2(z)/\delta \times \delta},$$

and this holds for every possible value of the unit of resolution, δ . On reducing δ to zero, we obtain the expression

$$f(x) = \frac{f_1(x) f_2(x)}{\int f_1(z) f_2(z) dz} \quad (3)$$

as the unique equation describing the result when combining acceptable PDFs $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ formed independently for the same fixed quantity.

Equation (3) is a result that is noteworthy in its own right, because the idea of combining different probability distributions for the same quantity has received considerable attention, e.g., (French, 1985)(Genest and Zidek, 1986)(Clemen and Winkler, 2007). There are various contexts in which such a combination might be sought: for example, the distributions could be deemed to be objective and to encode different sets of (true)

information or they could be subjective distributions due to different experts or even different non-experts. Many of the solutions suggested in the literature seem to focus on the properties of the resulting combination, not on the meaning and logic behind the method of combination. In our problem, we have considered the logic that relates to our context, and the corresponding combined PDF is seen to be a *logarithmic (opinion) pool* with unit weights. (The problem addressed here relates to, what might loosely be described as, the task of combining ‘different opinions of the same person’. A provocative but logical result for the contrasting task of combining ‘opinions of different people’ is given elsewhere (Willink, 2022, Appendix).)

Equation (3) is similar to the expression of Bayes’ Theorem if f_1 happened to be the prior PDF in a sampling experiment, which would be

$$f(x) = \frac{f_1(x) \ell(x|\text{data})}{\int f_1(z) \ell(z|\text{data}) dz}$$

with ℓ being the likelihood function. The receipt of f_2 acts multiplicatively on f_1 , just as receipt of the likelihood function acts multiplicatively on f_1 . Updating belief on receipt of the PDF f_2 is ‘learning by reading a new book’, whereas updating on receipt of the likelihood function is ‘learning by experience’.

4.1.1 Comment: the need for the discrete formulation

The derivation of (3) involves discrete variables and probability mass functions, not just the underlying continuous variables and probability density functions. The reason for this relates to a legitimate criticism of an earlier derivation of (3), where the analysis was conducted only with continuous quantities θ_1 and θ_2 (Willink, 2006). The condition involved in the conditional probability was “ $\theta_1 = \theta_2$ ”, so the equation analogous to (1) was (in our notation)

$$\text{pr} \left(\theta_1 = \theta_2 = x \mid \theta_1 = \theta_2 \right) = \frac{f_1(x) f_2(x)}{\int f_1(z) f_2(z) dz}, \quad (4)$$

which describes a probability density, not a probability. This equation was used to obtain (3). But the step by which (4) was presented was faulty because the event “ $\theta_1 = \theta_2$ ” has probability zero and the practice of calculating a probability conditional on an event with zero probability is open to Borel’s paradox, as was

pointed out by Grientschnig and Lira (2014). The step now taken of forming the conditional probability with discrete variables avoids the relevance of Borel’s paradox because the denominator in (1) and (2) is never zero. Moreover, Borel’s paradox has no relevance to the subsequent step of passing to the limit to obtain the result for continuous variables, (3). More details are available elsewhere (Willink, 2021, Section 2.3). (If there is a deeper result showing that a continuous bivariate probability density function collapses to the normalized profile along the diagonal cross-section when the two variables are found to be equal, without being subject to Borel’s paradox, then this would simplify the derivation of (3).)

4.2 Transformation of the variable implies a contradiction

The analysis has led to the following result: if $f_{1\theta}(x)$ and $f_{2\theta}(x)$ are the PDFs attributed to a quantity θ to accurately represent two disjoint sets of information or impressions about θ then the PDF to accurately represent the union of the sets obeys

$$f_{12\theta}(x) \propto f_{1\theta}(x)f_{2\theta}(x). \quad (5)$$

Now, suppose that the particular quantity of interest is $\lambda = h(\theta)$, where h is a monotonic function. For example, we might have $\lambda = \theta^2$ as in Section 2, or we might wish to measure the conductivity of a material instead of its resistivity, the two being related by $\lambda = 1/\theta$. As is well known, if the PDF attributed to θ is $f_\theta(x)$ then the PDF attributed to λ must be

$$f_\lambda(y) = f_\theta(x) \left| \frac{dx}{dy} \right| \quad y = h(x). \quad (6)$$

So, if there are two disjoint sets of influences about θ then the PDF attributable to λ can be found from the input PDFs $f_{1\theta}(x)$ and $f_{2\theta}(x)$ in two stages by applying equations of the ‘combination’ form (5) and the ‘transformation’ form (6). These operations represent steps of logical reasoning with summable sets of influences — so it is legitimate to combine first and then transform, and it is also legitimate to transform first and then combine: the result must be the same because all that is being carried out is the aggregation and re-expression of existing information and impressions.

Combining the PDFs $f_{1\theta}(x)$ and $f_{2\theta}(x)$ before transforming from θ to λ gives the intermediate result (5)

and the final PDF

$$f_{12\lambda}(y) \propto f_{1\theta}(x)f_{2\theta}(x) \left| \frac{dx}{dy} \right|, \quad (7)$$

but transforming from θ to λ before combining gives the intermediate result $f_{j\lambda}(y) = f_{j\theta}(x) |dx/dy|$ for $j = 1, 2$ and the final PDF

$$f_{12\lambda}(y) \propto f_{1\theta}(x)f_{2\theta}(x) \left| \frac{dx}{dy} \right|^2. \quad (8)$$

The combined PDFs (7) and (8) differ if $h(\cdot)$ is non-linear, as with the simple relationships $\lambda = \theta^2$ and $\lambda = 1/\theta$. Yet both PDFs are derived from statement 1, from the idea that the formation of PDFs must follow sensible reasoning, and from subsequent correct use of probability theory — so they should be the same. This is the contradiction that has been demonstrated in the measurement literature. In essence, it is the same contradiction as that demonstrated by the new argument in Section 2. The conclusion to be drawn is that statement 1 is not universally valid with unknown constants that exist on continuous scales. It applies whether the analysis involve statements of ‘necessary probability’ or ‘subjective probability’.

4.3 Criticisms of the analysis

Many readers will assume that there must be something incorrect in the argument that has been used to demonstrate the contradiction. But the argument in Section 4 has been seen by Bayesian statisticians and has been published elsewhere, and no meaningful rebuttal has come to light. The two complaints that I have received are paraphrased as follows:

- i. ‘Disjoint sets of influences do not exist in practice.’ (This was the criticism alluded to earlier.)
- ii. ‘The inconsistency in Section 4.2 is avoided if (3) is replaced by a logarithmic pool with exponents summing to 1’, i.e., by the equation

$$f(x) = \frac{f_1(x)^a f_2(x)^{1-a}}{\int f_1(z)^a f_2(z)^{1-a} dz}. \quad (9)$$

The first criticism was off-the-cuff, and it was unrelated to the theory of inference. The second criticism fails to engage with the logic that shows (3) to be the *unique* result for the problem stated. It proposes a solution

with a certain mathematical property, but not the property of logical justification. And its inadequacy is further emphasized when we observe a lack of associativity: when combining two distributions in an unprejudiced manner the value of a in (9) would be 0.5, so when combining three distributions one-by-one in two applications of (9) the result would not be invariant to the ordering of the distributions.

In summary, if we are to identify something incorrect in the reasoning by which the conclusion has been reached then deeper analysis is required.

5 Attempts at explanation

The analysis in this paper has demonstrated a contradiction that seems to invalidate the basis of much Bayesian statistical practice. Yet the logic involved in a coherent subjective Bayesian analysis has long been regarded as unquestionable. So what explanation can be given for the existence of this contradiction? This section presents three different approaches to explanation, two that consider the ideas of axioms and one argues more mathematically, with each being verbal and informal. These explanations are to be viewed as incomplete. They are offered as first steps to explaining the existence of the contradiction in the hope that they will assist readers to engage with the important issue raised in this paper. These explanations in no way invalidate the conclusion put forward, but they do potentially provide places for someone to start when arguing against the conclusion.

5.1 Are the axioms of probability obeyed?

Our first attempt at explaining how the contradiction can exist relates to the idea that identifying degree of belief with subjective probability is only legitimate if degree of belief obeys the axioms of probability. To see one way in which the statistical community has considered this, we refer to the influential book of Lindley (1965). Lindley (p. 6) sets out axioms of probability with the text:

For certain pairs of events, A and B , a real number $p(A|B)$ is defined and called the *probability* of A given B . These numbers satisfy the following axioms:

Axiom 1. $0 \leq p(A|B) \leq 1$ and $p(A|A) = 1$.

Axiom 2. If the events in $\{A_n\}$ are exclusive given B then

$$p(\sum_n A_n | B) = \sum_n p(A_n | B).$$

Axiom 3 $p(C|AB)p(A|B) = p(AC|B)$.

Subsequently (pp. 29ff), he describes what is meant by a numerical degree of belief and argues mathematically (pp. 34–36) that the idea of degree of belief obeys these axioms, the implication being that we can apply the theory of probability with degrees of belief. But Axiom 3 relates to any three events A, B, C , and Lindley’s demonstration uses two hypotheses, H_1 and H_2 , and one set of information, E . So the identification of degree of belief with probability does not seem to be proven when there is one hypothesis H and two sets of information E and E' (which seems to correspond to our situation of a single unknown and two sets of influences), as for example in the scenario he alludes to on page 40. Lindley (p. 32) does describe E as “our accumulated knowledge of events and hypotheses at some point in time”, one implication being that E might be written as H_3 . But if that is the case then what is the importance of differentiating an E from an H symbolically? Would the proof hold and have meaning with the triplet H, E and E' instead? So the present author is not convinced that Lindley has shown that every set of entities that satisfies the definition of a degree of belief obeys Axiom 3.

The present author has also found no satisfying demonstration that degree of belief can be identified with probability in more recent texts either. For example, O’Hagan (1988) considers subjective probability and derives two laws with “the minimum of fuss” (p. 1). His ‘multiplication law’ corresponds to the third axiom above and, as with the analysis of Lindley, the demonstration involves two hypotheses and one set of experiences. From other writers, there is acceptance on the basis that the result has been demonstrated earlier. For example, Box and Tiao (1973) simply imply that they are following earlier writers in their use of probability (p. 14). In a statement in which the immediate context is that of decision theory, Gelman et al. (2014) just state “Then reasonable axioms (ordering, transitivity, and so on) imply that uncertainty *must* be represented in terms of probability. We view this normative rationale as suggestive but not compelling” (pp. 12,13). Somewhat in contrast, Bolstad and Curran (2017) argue for the use of probability by appealing

to a result of R. T. Cox that a system or ‘plausibilities’ with certain desirable properties could only be realized by identifying plausibility with probability (pp. 61-62).

In short, my argument is that the claim “degree of belief obeys the axioms of probability” does not seem to have been proven for the situation where, as is reasonable, the degrees of belief are those that would correspond to different sets of influences or experiences E and E' , such as those envisaged (albeit obliquely) by Lindley on his page 40 and such as those described in this paper.

5.2 Anyway, an axiom of rational reasoning supersedes the axioms of probability

Our second approach is to argue that the concepts of degree of belief and probability are secondary in both authority and chronology to the concept of rationality in reasoning – in which case the question raised in Section 5.1 becomes a red herring and its answer becomes irrelevant. Instead, we assert that accurate reasoning is more than just the accurate calculation of probabilities.

The contradiction can be demonstrated because we have required the formation of a person’s assessment of θ to obey a principle of rational aggregation. Consider, for example, that it is 10 o’clock in the morning and that you are wondering if it will be raining at noon. You experience a number of influences, which we represent here by three.

- You recognize that it is 10 o’clock in the morning.
- At the moment, the sky appears clear and blue to you.
- You recall that the sky seemed clear and blue at 10 o’clock yesterday but that it was raining at noon.

It does not matter what order you become aware of these facts of impressions: if you are thinking rationally then, in regard to the hypothesis that it will be raining at noon today, the end result on your consciousness when given all these influences will be the same whatever the order. And if you are not thinking rationally then why should anybody (including yourself) trust your judgement? The requirement for rationality is the basis of any analysis: if you are being rational then your consciousness obeys rules of aggregation and commutativity that will give meaning to your quantitative judgements.

This principle of the rational aggregation of influences has been proposed without any mention of the ideas of ‘degree of belief’ and ‘probability’. It precedes those other concepts in this argument, and so it has at least the same level of authority as any appeal to degree of belief or probability. It exists in the realm of reasoning, not in the realm of probability, so it has no connection with any axiom of probability. Therefore, just showing that a degree of belief obeys the axioms of probability fails to engage with this principle or axiom of rational reasoning. Therefore, any demonstration — complete or incomplete, correct or incorrect — that degrees of belief obey the axioms of probability is insufficient to invalidate our conclusion.

When we subsequently consider the idea of reasoning using strength of belief, the argument can be summarized and restated as follows. One ‘axiom’ of reasoning is that an acceptable degree of belief will be fixed by the totality of what is experienced and will be unaffected by the order in which the things were experienced or the lengths of time between these experiences, (the passing of time itself being one of the experiences in question). When degree of belief is treated as probability, this axiom seems to be in conflict with the accepted axioms of probability.

So, there appears to be a mode of reasoning that is unable to be represented by the theory of probability, in which case probability might not be an adequate tool to fully describe uncertainty in all situations. In relation to this suggestion, we observe that Gelman et al. (2014) give one definition of probability in terms of degree of belief, comment that this concept obeys the axioms, and then themselves suggest that this concept has some difficulties. They ask the curious question “How can you assign exact odds [in a bet] if you are not sure?”, which is a question that seems to suggest a lack of trust in the idea of subjective probability. In the summarizing paragraph of the relevant section (p. 13) they write:

All of these considerations suggest that probabilities may be a reasonable approach to summarizing uncertainty in applied statistics, but the ultimate proof is in the success of the applications.

The lack of force in this statement came as a surprise to me. The authors appear to be leaving the door open for probability to be found inadequate as a universal tool, which would be a conclusion consistent with the contradiction identified here. (Gelman et al (p. 25) do acknowledge that the foundations of probability and Bayesian statistics are an important topic that they have treated only briefly.)

The lack of appeal to theory in the suggestion contained within the above quotation from Gelman et al

is also consistent with this possibility. The suggestion that “probabilities may be a reasonable approach to summarizing uncertainty in applied statistics” can be interpreted (or misinterpreted) as meaning “As long as the method works, it is OK”. This may be a good principle for an engineer — who can observe whether the building stands up or falls down — but it is not so good for someone concerned with the foundations of inference and decision-making in a scientific context. It requires a definition of what it means for a method of analysis to result in “success”. What does demonstrable success look like in a problem of inference where the true value remains unknown? The analysis here has demonstrated the existence of a logical contradiction, so that there must be many problems in which the method of assigning PDFs to constants cannot possibly be said to be successful.

5.3 The extent of the problem — a clue

Our third approach to explaining how the contradiction can arise involves the fact that the conclusion has only been presented for constants on continuous scales: the arguments given do not apply to the attribution of probability mass functions to constants on discrete scales. As we now show, with discrete variables, we do not observe a contradiction, we only observe a counter-intuitive result that can be tolerated. But the existence of this result seems to give some indication of the genesis of the contradiction.

Consider the idea of a subjective probability that hypothesis H is true, which we will call a ‘probability of H’. Suppose that P_1 and P_2 are the probabilities of H induced in the mind of a person by two sets of disjoint influences. Then, by the same argument that was applied to the discrete variable in Section 4 and illustrated in Figure 2, the probability P that the person must attribute to H when both sets of influences are experienced is

$$P = \frac{P_1 P_2}{P_1 P_2 + (1 - P_1)(1 - P_2)}. \quad (10)$$

As in Section 4.1, we can obtain this result by considering holding probabilities for different hypotheses H_1 and H_2 and then learning that the two hypotheses are actually the same. This situation is depicted for the probabilities $P_1 = 0.6$ and $P_2 = 0.7$ in Figure 4, where Figures 4(a) and 4(b) are analogous to Figures 3(a) and 3(b) but where the diagrams resemble tables, so that the leading diagonal is oriented differently. In this situation, we find that $P = 0.42/(0.42 + 0.12) = 7/9$.

Figure 4: Example joint probability mass functions about two hypotheses H_1 and H_2 and about two categorical variables Ω_1 and Ω_2 when there are two disjoint sets of influences. (Empty cells have mass zero.)

(a) $p_1(H_1) = 0.6$ and $p_2(H_2) = 0.7$.

(b) Same as (a) but after learning that H_1 is the same as H_2 .

(c) $(p_{\Omega_1}(A), p_{\Omega_1}(B), p_{\Omega_1}(C)) = (0.6, 0.3, 0.1)$ and $(p_{\Omega_2}(A), p_{\Omega_2}(B), p_{\Omega_2}(C)) = (0.7, 0.2, 0.1)$.

(d) Same as (c) but after learning that Ω_1 is equal to Ω_2 .

Now suppose that the problem instead involves categorical variables Ω_1 and Ω_2 with potential values A, B and C, that one set of influences induces the PMF with probabilities $P_{\Omega_1}(A) = 0.6$, $P_{\Omega_1}(B) = 0.3$ and $P_{\Omega_1}(C) = 0.1$, and that a disjoint set induces the PMF with probabilities $P_{\Omega_2}(A) = 0.7$, $P_{\Omega_2}(B) = 0.2$ and $P_{\Omega_2}(C) = 0.1$. Let H be the hypothesis $\Omega = A$, in which case these PMFs are consistent with the probabilities of 0.6 and 0.7 in our example. The same argument applies, and we obtain the situation depicted in Figure 4(c) and Figure 4(d), which gives the result $P(A) = P(H \text{ is true}) = 6/7$. So there is an apparent anomaly: simply by considering the hypotheses (in this case the complementary hypothesis \bar{H}) to be more granular, we obtain a different result for the combined probability of H. Figure 4 illustrates this how this occurs: (i) the cells

along the diagonal are more numerous in Figures 4(c) and 4(d) than they are in Figures 4(a) and 4(b), and (ii) some of the area that represents a multiplication of non-zero probabilities in Figure 4(b) is empty in Figure 4(d), which leads to the result in the more detailed analysis, which is $0.42/0.49 = 6/7$, being greater than the result in the binary case, which is $0.42/0.54 = 7/9$.

On reflection, we can see that this result makes sense, and it becomes a counter-intuitive result, not a contradiction. Suppose that one set of influences induces a PMF in which the probability attributed to the event ‘ $\Omega = B$ ’ is zero and that the other induces a PMF in which the probability attributed to the event ‘ $\Omega = C$ ’ is zero. Then, by the first, the individual concludes that Ω cannot possibly be B and, by the second, they conclude that Ω cannot possibly be C, which only leaves A. The result must then be $P(A) = P(H \text{ is true}) = 1$, which can never be obtained from (10) unless $P_1 = P_2 = 1$. We reach the conclusion that *when a hypothesis H is the union of different mutually exclusive sub-hypotheses (as when H is an inequality with a discrete numerical variable) the probability of H being true after combination of two disjoint sets of influences is not given by (10)*. Instead, the probability is found with the help of the probabilities attributable to the sub-hypotheses, in this case the sub-hypotheses ‘ $\Omega = B$ ’ and ‘ $\Omega = C$ ’. Therefore, a statement analogous to statement 8 that might be made for PMFs would be incorrect. It is because of this that we do not claim that the contradiction applies to discrete probability distributions.

To see how this potentially gives an explanation of the contradiction existing with continuous variables, we liken the splitting of the binary variable into the ternary variable — the splitting of the truth-status of H into the value of Ω — to the uneven stretching or transformation of the x -axis that occurred in Section 4.2 when we transformed our interest from θ to interest in $\lambda \equiv h(\theta)$ for non-linear h . In the discrete case, the splitting brings to our attention a phenomenon that can be identified and accepted as a counter-intuitive result but, in the continuous case, the transformation brings to our attention a contradiction that, seemingly, cannot be dismissed in the same way.

5.3.1 An aside

Before concluding, let us observe that (10) can be expressed as

$$\frac{P_{12}}{1 - P_{12}} = \frac{P_1}{1 - P_1} \cdot \frac{P_2}{1 - P_2}.$$

This shows that, (if the attribution of a probability to the truth-status of a hypothesis H is legitimate), *the odds ratio for the truth of H based on the two disjoint sets of influences is the product of the odds ratios based on the individual sets of influences.* This simple result does not seem widely known.

6 Conclusion

Probability is a mathematical construct, and it should be interpreted as such. The debate between frequentist and Bayesian statisticians is not about the interpretation of probability: it is about the legitimate role or roles of probability. It is not about how we interpret probability, it is about how probability can be used to interpret our world, it is about interpretation *by* probability. In this paper, the presumption that we can legitimately and meaningfully use a probability density function to describe our belief about an unknown constant — which is expressed in statement 1— has been examined, and the conclusion has been reached from elementary reasoning and basic probability theory that it is incorrect in the general context. The principle on which this conclusion relies is that the formation of a distribution for a constant θ must obey sensible rules, just as any subsequent analysis of experimental data must obey sensible rules.

The analysis has shown that, if we accept the idea that influences on the mind are to be aggregated according to reasonable and elementary rules, then a logical contradiction exists when integrated probability density is used to describe degree of belief. Combining sets of influences and then applying a transformation of variables leads to a different result from transforming first and combining second: yet both orderings of reasoning are logically acceptable, and they should give the same answer. This contradiction would not be observable if statement 1 were universally true. So, either statement 1 is false or the distributions it refers to cannot be trusted, or both. The conclusion reached does not extend to the idea of attributing a probability

mass function to an unknown quantity on a discrete scale. But the existence of this conclusion for continuous variables must raise questions about that practice also.

The claim being made in this paper is not just another claim that the personal nature of ‘subjective Bayesian statistics’ invalidates its scientific authority or just another demonstration that the various principles of ‘objective Bayesian statistics’ lead to anomalous and unacceptable results, e.g., (Willink, 2013, Ch. 13). Rather, it is a criticism of the very foundation of any form of analysis in which constants are considered to have continuous probability distributions — so the conclusion also applies to the problematic field of fiducial inference. The argument has been based on statements 2–8, which (with the exception of statement 4) have been presented as corollaries to statement 1. The argument involves a commitment to upholding the idea of rational reasoning and an appeal to elementary ideas from probability theory. The statements that form the argument here are numbered to allow any criticism of the argument to be identified clearly: legitimate criticism must be able to identify the precise location of a flaw in the reasoning. The important conclusion presented in this paper requires discussion in the statistical community, especially as much of the work has already been presented in the literature of measurement science.

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